

Database construction on planktons and biofouling organisms

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Abstract. We focused on the plankton and biofouling biomasses in Tashue Bay (Hong Kong Ocean Park), Shenzhen Bay, the Lamma Island, and the Swires Institute of Marine Science Laboratory. Photo IDs, classifications, dates, locations, samplers, and magnifications of the 684 pictures were recorded. They were ordered in groups by names. Rarefaction curves and frequency charts were created to record biodiversity. We concluded that Taishue Bay (Hong Kong) has more plankton diversity than Shenzhen Bay, and the SWIMS sea region has higher biofouling diversity than Lamma Island fish farm. The database could serve as the basis for the development of auto-detection by artificial intelligence.

1. Introduction

A database is a library where information is stored, retrieved, and referenced. To be specific, researchers could utilize the data collection to compare with previous or future studies. Here, our goal is to discover the biodiversity of plankton and biofouling organisms in the four different sampling locations. We focused on recording and comparing the plankton and biofouling biodiversity in Tashue Bay (Hong Kong Ocean Park), Shenzhen Bay, the Lamma Island, and the Swires Institute of Marine Science Laboratory, which are all within the region of the South China Sea. Sampling equipment such as plankton net and the light trap were used, and the samples are photographed by camera-attached optical microscopes while documented.

2. Methods and research

2.1 Sampling

The sample were collected in three different places to study the biodiversity of China's ocean. Our first sampling was on 26th June, 2023 afternoon and the location was the Dasha River Dam. This dam was where Dasha River intersects with Shenzhen Bay's sea water (22.520529, 113.955306). This sampling was done by the plankton net. The plankton net's pore size was 70 μm . We threw and dragged back 5 times to make sure we got enough plankton.

Our second sampling is in on 28th June, 2023 night (8:00~9:00) and the location was the same as the first sampling. This sampling was done by light trap. We put it under the water for 5~10 minutes to collect plankton.

Then, we moved to Hong Kong to finish our sampling. We went to a fish farm raft in Lamma Island (GPS: 22.208841288559796, 114.13239639353226) to collect the bio-fouling organisms which grown on the fish net. We collected mostly the fouling organisms such as mussel and barnacle.

The next sampling station was SWIMS (Swire Institute of Marine Science), and the GPS coordinate is 2.207685, 114.259741. We collected organisms which grown on the ARMS system, which is a device that SWIMS researchers put under the sea to let the benthos grow. It is composed with several solid broads that could provide a space for benthos.

2.2 Photos labeling

All information in the photo was recorded in the excel data spreadsheet which has five columns. Photo_ID represent the file name of each photo in the database; classification represents the taxonomy information of the object in the photo; "date" represents the date of sampling; "location" represents the text or when possible, GPS location of the

sampling site; "magnification" represents the magnification when the picture of the sample was taken; At last, "sampler" recorded the person who obtained the sample."

Each photo ID contains different information. For example, the photo labeled as "18_COP_20230628_DS_S_4X" mean that "18" was the number of the order of the picture taken in a certain location; COP" is the abbreviation for copepod, and more specificity about the organism was listed under a column named "classifications"; "The numbers "20230628" was the date the sample was collected; "DS" is denote the location information, which in this case "DS" stand for Dasha River; "S" was just extra information added to show that the sample was collected in the salt water region of the Dasha River; Finally, "4x" was the magnification when the picture of the sample was taken.

3. Results

3.1 Planktons Data of Dasha River and Taishue Bay

From the three diagrams below (Figure 1-3), Hong Kong Taishue Bay's biodiversity is much higher than Dasha River's biodiversity. The species number of the Dasha River (Figure 2 & 3) is 17 in total including both plankton net and light trap. Representative photos of species listed in Figure 2 & 3 are shown in Figure 4 & 5. In contrast, the Hong Kong Ocean Park (Taishue Bay, Figure 1) has 50 species in total, which is almost 3 times of the Dasha River's biodiversity.

As the first and second diagram shows (Figure 1), diatom is the dominant species of Taishue Bay. Not only that, in our sampling, we observed 7 different kinds of diatoms. In those diatoms, the "Diatom-Cha.0" has the largest number (Figure 1).

Back to Dasha River, as we mentioned, the biodiversity of Shenzhen Bay was much lower than Taishue Bay. Its biomass was mostly composed of copepod and rotifer. Both light trap sampling and plankton net sampling showed that copepod is the dominant species (Figure 2 & 3). Therefore, we can find that those two nearby ocean regions have a very different environment and biodiversity.

Figure 1. A statistic of specimens collected in HongKong Ocean Park

Figure 2. A statistic of specimens collected in Dasha River by Plankton Net

Figure 3. A statistic of specimens collected in Dasha River by Light Trap

Figure 4. Plankton specimen pictures from Dasha River plankton samples. **A.** Copepod Cyclopoida; **B.** Copepod Calanoida; **C.** Copepod Harpacticoida; **D.** Barnacle larva; **E.** Ostracod; **F.** Rotifer sp. **D**; **g.** *Daphina*; **H.** Copepod larva; **I.** Diatom sp.1; **J.** Rotifer sp. **E**; **K.** Green Algae *Pediastrum*; **L.** Polychaete larva; **M.** Rotifer sp. **B**; **N.** Green Algae *Dimorphococcus*; **O.** Rotifer sp. **C**; **P.** Diatom sp. 2; **Q.** Rotifer sp. **A**; **R.** UNKNOWN 2.

Figure 5. Other plankton specimen pictures from the Dasha River plankton samples. **A.** Unknown **C**; **B.** Unknown **G**; **C.** Unknown **E**; **D.** Unknown **D**; **E.** UNKNOWN 1; **F.** Unknown **A**.

The rarefaction below further reveals how diverse Taishue Bay’s plankton biomass (Figure 6). The rarity of the

biomass in Taishue Bay is increasing even though the curve is getting to the end. The plankton net sampling, in the Dasha River, has a lower growing frequency and the plankton we get by the same method, which are less than Taishue Bay. The light trap sampling's rarefaction curve is barely growing because it uses the phototaxis of plankton to attract them. In conclusion, the Hong Kong Bay area has greater biodiversity than Shenzhen Bay and more sampling is needed.

Figure 6. Rarefaction curve of diversity of specimens collected from Dasha River using plankton net (orange line), using light trap (blue line) and from Taishue Bay outside Hong Kong Ocean Park (yellowish line).

3.2 The Marine organism of the Lamma Island and SWIMS

These two diagrams reveal the differences between biofouling marine organisms and normal growing marine organisms (Figure 7, 8). In the Lamma Island, we find many polychaetae and mussels (Figure 7), but the number of mussels was so large that it becomes uncountable. The biofouling organisms are growing on the fish net of Fisher's village. The nets provide a suitable space that mussels to spread easily. And the mussels will also give a good environment to let polychaete tubeworms grow and reproduce. Unlike the fish net, the ARMS which had been put down the sea doesn't make a suitable way to let the benthos such as mussels. The ARMS's dominant species are sea snails because the board in the ARMS is the perfect home for them (Figure 5). Also, there aren't many crabs who live on the fish net due to the place, but the space between the ARMS's board promotes the spreading of crab. That is why we observed more crabs on ARMS than biofouling fishing net. By analyzing biodiversity in different places, we discover that different environments will create differences in biodiversity.

Figure 7. Specimen diversity in ARMS retrieved from SWIMS.

Figure 8. Specimen diversity in the biofouling communities in the Lamma Island fishfarm raft.

We observe from the underneath diagram that even SWIMS's marine organism number are less than Lamma island's biofouling organisms (Figure 7), yet SWIMS's biomass has a richer diversity. Combined with the biodiversity graph above, we think that SWIMS's sea region has a greater diversity than Lamma Island's biofouling area.

Figure 9. The comparison of sample diversity rarefaction between SWIMS and Lamma Island.

4. Discussion

4.1 ARMS VS. Lamma Island

We believe that the two places' facilities make biodiversity different. The rope's fiber in the Fisher village gives a solid base for mussels because the mussel's byssus can easily stack in the fiber. In addition, the mussel has a very strong reproduction ability. The female mussel can lay 25 million eggs at one time. And mussels have two reproductive periods: spring and autumn. With its impressive ability, the mussel becomes a dominant species of biofouling community easily [6]. In the last century, the mussel had already been an invasive species of Hong Kong. Then, the mussel will become a home for the barnacles. Therefore, the biofouling community will mostly have lower biodiversity than ARMS.

4.2 Shenzhen vs Taishue Bay

The difference in biodiversity in Taishue Bay and Shenzhen Bay is due to the way we sampled. During the light trapped sampling, we used blue light to attract species that are positive phototaxis. According to the article "Spectral Sensitivity of Vertically Migrating Copepods", light is critical to the vertical migration of four different species of Calanoid copepods [1]. In addition, adult *Tigriopus Japonicus*, a type of harpacticoid copepod, are positive phototaxis at an intensity of $2.0\text{W}/\text{m}^2$ regardless of different kinds of light used [2]. Thus, the different types of copepods that dominated the results of the light trapped data are rather sensitive and photo-philic. Another reason for the disparity between the biodiversity in Taishue Bay and Shenzhen Bay is because of the pollution in Shenzhen Bay. To be specific, the amount of metal contamination such as and Cd in the waters of Shenzhen Bay can cause moderate ecological risk [3]. Moreover, other pollutants like inorganic nitrogen and active phosphate can have serious impact on Shenzhen Bay's water quality by reaching a load of 76.2t and 283.8t [4]. In conclusion, Shenzhen Bay has a lot of metal and non-metal contamination that can cause harm to the diversity of plankton organisms.

4.3 Application perspectives

Our database could be useful for environmental protection. For example, our database comparison between Shenzhen Bay and Taishue Bay reveals the difference between two environments. Shenzhen Bay is heavily polluted, but Taishue Bay is less polluted. Their differences in biodiversity are very likely related to pollution. By observing our analysis, those environmentalists will know that the pollution is already affecting the biodiversity of Shenzhen

Bay so that they can make some protection as quickly as possible. Also, the recording of our database could be a contrast for other scientists. They can contrast their database with our database. Then, they will know the difference between two distinct databases.

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